

Usher syndrome 1C (autosomal recessive, severe) / USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : USH1C encodes harmonin, a protein that in humans, that is expressed in sensory cells of the inner ear and retina. Mutations at the USH1C locus are known to cause Usher syndrome type 1c and nonsyndromic sensorineural deafness. It is not known whether USH1C plays any role in meningiomas, however Patel et al. [1] record upregulation of USH1C in meningiomas. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of USH1C, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

*ML dicoveries of USH1C synergy in Meningiomas

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Keywords: USH1C, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Usher syndrome

In 1914, Scottish ophthalmologist Charles Howard Usher wrote a treatise in Usher [13] based on his findings on a survey of 69 individuals who suffered from visual problems associated with deafness. He demonstrated that the disease was inherited, and that parents passed the condition onto their children. Wikipedia [14] describes his discovery as a continuation of the work done by German ophthalmologists Albrecht von Graefe and Richard Liebreich, who did extensive research of retinitis pigmentosa and its link to deafness in the mid-19th century.

Wikipedia [15] state that Usher syndrome, also known as Hallgren syndrome, Usher-Hallgren syndrome, retinitis pigmentosa-dysacusis syndrome or dystrophia retinae dysacusis syndrome, is a rare genetic disorder caused by a mutation in any one of at least 11 genes resulting in a combination of hearing loss and visual impairment. It is the most common cause of deafblindness and is at present incurable.

Further, Usher syndrome is classified into three subtypes (I, II, and III) based on the genes responsible (and the mutations in them) and the onset of deafness. These mutations are inherited in an autosomal recessive pattern. More specifically the Usher syndrome type I sensory defect involves sensorineural deafness, vestibular dysfunction, and blindness due to progressive retinitis pigmentosa.

Keats and Corey [16] provides an detailed review on the Usher syndromes.

1.3. USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C)

Harmonin, encoded by USH1C gene is expressed in sensory cells of the inner ear and retina. Mutations in USH1C are known to cause Usher syndrome type 1c and nonsyndromic sensorineural deafness. In sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) accounts for 90% of the reported hearing loss and the root cause lies in the inner ear, sensory organ (cochlea and associated structures), or the vestibulocochlear nerve (cranial nerve VIII) (Matsunaga [17]). A schematic diagram of mechano-electrical transduction in hair cells involving the Harmonin, has been provided in figure 2.

Harmonin contains a PDZ domain, which assists in attaching the protein to the cell membrane and to cytoskeletal components. The PDZ structural domain is consists of 80-90 amino-acids found in the signaling proteins (Lee and Zheng [18]).

A locus (USH1C) for one form of Usher syndrome type I was previously assigned to the short arm of chromosome 11 through linkage studies in the Acadian population of southwestern Louisiana. Via linkage analyses of a set of microsatellite markers in 27 Acadian families Keats et al. [19] provide evidence that USH1C lies between D11S861 and D11S928. They observed that three markers (D11S419, D11S921, and D11S899) that lie between the flanking markers showed no recombination with USH1C, and all 54 chromosomes with the abnormal allele at the disease locus had identical alleles for D11S419 and D11S921. Their results suggested that USH1C was in the 2-3-cM interval between D11S861 and D11S899.

Jain et al. [20] mapped autosomal recessive nonsyndromic sensorineural deafness segregating in a large consanguineous Indian family to chromosome 11p14p15.1, thus defining a new locus,DFNB18. They obtained a maximum lod score of 4.4 at $\theta = 0$ for the polymorphic microsatellite marker D11S1888. Their haplotype analysis localized this gene between markers D11S1307 and D11S2368, which was approximately 1.6 cM and encompassed the region of USH1C. Thus, they postulated that DFNB18 and USH1C were allelic variants of the same gene.

Patients with renal and colon cancer frequently develop IgG autoantibodies toward the NY-CO-38/PDZ-73 antigen, a protein of 652 amino acids (73 kDa) which contains three copies of the PDZ protein-protein interaction domain. Translation of the NY-CO-38 cDNA by Scanlan et al. [21] gave a protein of 652 amino acids (337 Da) with three

Figure 2: A schematic diagram of Mechanoelectrical transduction in hair cells by ©Cochleae on <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/USH1C> under CC-BY-SA Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>). Caption by Cochleae - Mechanoelectrical transduction in hair cells. (1) Mechanically gated ion channel (orange) is attached to a tip link, which consists of homodimers of cadherin 23 and protocadherin 15. (2) Inside a stereocilium, harmonin (green) links the cytoplasmic terminus of cadherin 23 (blue) to myosin 7A (black), a motor protein that tightly binds filamentous actin of the cytoskeleton (pink). (3) The vibrational energy in sound waves physically displaces the bundle toward the tallest stereocilium, increasing tension in the tip link that forces the ion channel to open. (4) Influx of the cations calcium (Ca^{2+} ; red) and potassium (K^{+} ; yellow) depolarizes the hair cell to trigger neurotransmitter release. Created with BioRender.com.

PDZ domains as well as a possible PEST protein degradation motif, a coiled-coil domain, and amino terminal and carboxyl terminal domains with no known similarities. They named this protein PDZ-73 (Now - USH1C). They found that the gene encoding PDZ-73 mapped to chromosome 11p15.4-p15.1 and identified additional tissue-specific isoforms i.e - • PDZ-45, which lacked the third PDZ domain and the putative PEST protein degradation motif; • PDZ-54 and PDZ-59, which also lack the third PDZ domains and have unique carboxyl terminal amino acids and are expressed in brain, kidney, bladder, colon cancer and renal cancer; and • PDZ-37 isoform, which contains only the third PDZ domain, that is expressed in the central nervous system.

Six different USH1 loci have been reported and Verpy et al. [22] report a gene underlying USH1C (MIM 276904), a USH1 subtype described in a population of Acadian descendants from Louisiana and in a Lebanese family. In a subtracted mouse cDNA library derived from inner ear sensory areas, they identified this gene (USH1C), encoding a PDZ-domain-containing protein, harmonin. In the mouse inner ear, they showed that only the sensory hair cells express harmonin. The inner ear USH1C transcripts predicted several harmonin isoforms, some containing an additional coiled-coil

domain and a proline- and serine-rich region. As several of these transcripts were absent from the eye, they hypothesized that USH1C also underlied the DFNB18 form of isolated deafness.

Bitner-Glindzicz et al. [23] identified three individuals from two consanguineous families with severe hyperinsulinism, profound congenital sensorineural deafness, enteropathy and renal tubular dysfunction. The molecular basis of the disorder is a homozygous 122-kb deletion of 11p14-15, which includes part of ABCC8 and overlaps with the locus for USH1C and DFNB18 (Jain et al. [20]). They observed that the centromeric boundary of this deletion included part of a gene shown to be mutated in families with type 1C Usher syndrome, and hence they assigned the name USH1C. They further observed that the pattern of expression of the USH1C protein was consistent with the clinical features exhibited by individuals with the contiguous gene deletion and with isolated Usher type 1C.

Several genetic loci have been linked to Usher syndrome type 1 (USH1), and four of the relevant genes have been identified which encode the myosin VIIa, the PDZ-domain protein harmonin, and the putative adhesion receptors cadherin 23 (CDH23) and protocadherin 15 (PCDH15). Siemens et al. [24] showed that CDH23 and harmonin form a protein complex where two PDZ domains in harmonin interacted with two complementary binding surfaces in the CDH23 cytoplasmic domain. Further, they observed that in the ear, CDH23 and harmonin were expressed in the stereocilia of hair cells, and in the retina within the photoreceptor cell layer. Because CDH23-deficient mice had splayed stereocilia, their data suggested that CDH23 and harmonin were part of a transmembrane complex that connects stereocilia into a bundle. Based on this, they predict that defects in the formation of this complex might disrupt stereocilia bundles and cause deafness in USH1 patients.

Deaf-blindness in three distinct genetic forms of USH1 is caused by defects in myosin VIIa, harmonin and cadherin 23. Boëda et al. [25] showed that harmonin and cadherin 23 were both present in the growing stereocilia and that they bound to each other. Further, they showed that harmonin b is an F-actin-bundling protein, which was likely to anchor cadherin 23 to the stereocilia microfilaments, thereby identifying a novel anchorage mode of the cadherins to the actin cytoskeleton. They also observed that harmonin b interacted with myosin VIIa directly, and was absent from the disorganized hair bundles of myosin VIIa mutant mice, thus pointing to the fact that myosin VIIa conveyed harmonin b along the actin core of the developing stereocilia. They thus hypothesized that the shaping of the hair bundle depend on a functional unit composed of myosin VIIa, harmonin b and cadherin 23 that was necessary to ensure the cohesion of the stereocilia.

Defects in myosin VIIa, harmonin (a PDZ domain protein), cadherin 23, protocadherin 15 and SANS (a putative scaffolding protein), underlie five forms of USH1. Mouse mutants for all these proteins exhibit disorganization of their hair bundle, which is the mechanotransduction receptive structure of the inner ear sensory cells, the cochlear and vestibular hair cells. After demonstrating that harmonin interacted with cadherin 23 and myosin VIIa, Adato et al. [26] addressed the extent of interactions between the five known USH1 proteins. They go on to establish the previously suggested SANS-harmonin interaction and found that SANS also bound to myosin VIIa. Their molecular characterization of the observed interactions indicated that through its binding to four

of the five USH1 proteins, the first PDZ domain (PDZ1) of harmonin played a crucial role in this network. Thus they hypothesized that via its binding to myosin VIIa and/or harmonin, SANS controlled the hair bundle cohesion and proper development via regulation of the traffic of USH1 proteins en route to the stereocilia.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [27] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [28] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [28].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [29]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of forming the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [30], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank}

Joachims [27] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [27]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [31], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine

ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. USH1C related synergies

Note - USH1C was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 ^{2nd} order combinations of USH1C were recorded.

3.1.1. USH1C - Individual genes

The following genes were found to show high rankings along with USH1C - mitochondrial calcium uniporter dominant negative subunit beta (MCUB), V-set and immunoglobulin domain containing 2 (VSIG2), tolloid like 1 (TLL1), mucolipin TRP cation channel 3 (MCOLN3), ST6 N-acetylgalactosaminide alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 2 (ST6GALNAC2), ST6 beta-galactoside alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 1 (ST6GAL1), calmodulin regulated spectrin associated protein family member 3 (CAMSAP3), calpain 6 (CAPN6), secretagogen, EF-hand calcium binding protein (SCGN), ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1 (ABCB1), solute carrier family 7 member 8 (SLC7A8), tolloid like 2 (TLL2), protein kinase C and casein kinase substrate in neurons 2 (PAC-SIN2), neurotensin receptor 1 (NTSR1), WAP four-disulfide core domain 2 (WFDC2), annexin A13 (ANXA13), glutamate ionotropic receptor kainate type subunit 5 (GRIK5), RUN domain containing 3B (RUNDC3B), sodium channel epithelial 1 subunit alpha (SCNN1A), FA complementation group E (FANCE), phosphatase and actin regulator 1 (PHACTR1), RNA binding motif protein 24 (RBM24), leucine rich repeat containing 31 (LRRC31), peroxisomal biogenesis factor 5 like (PEX5L), melanophilin (MLPH), nuclear receptor subfamily 5 group A member 2 (NR5A2), phospholipid phosphatase related 4 (PLPPR4), periplakin (PPL), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 12 (GALNT12), nuclear factor, erythroid 2 (NFE2), ATP binding cassette subfamily C member 4 (PEL blood group) (ABCC4), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 2 (PCSK2), tubulin alpha 4a (TUBA4A), G protein subunit alpha z (GNAZ), filamin C (FLNC), myosin VC (MYO5C), kallikrein related peptidase 8 (KLK8), fibroblast growth factor 13 (FGF13), proline rich and Gla domain 3 (PRRG3), argininosuccinate synthase 1 (ASS1), brain expressed X-linked 2 (BEX2), LARGE xylosyl- and glucuronyltransferase 1 (LARGE1), unc-79 homolog, NALCN channel complex subunit

(UNC79), BICD family like cargo adaptor 1 (BICDL1), HECT, C2 and WW domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2 (HECW2), epidermal growth factor (EGF), shisa like 1 (SHISAL1 / KIAA1644), collagen type II alpha 1 chain (COL2A1), SLAIN motif family member 1 (SLAIN1), MAM domain containing glycosylphosphatidylinositol anchor 2 (MDGA2), ring finger protein 157 (RNF157), solute carrier family 47 member 1 (SLC47A1), maelstrom spermatogenic transposon silencer (MAEL), sushi domain containing 4 (SUSD4), HHIP like 2 (HHIPL2), thrombospondin type 1 domain containing 7B (THSD7B), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 13 (GALNT13), coiled-coil domain containing 150 (CCDC150), immunoglobulin superfamily member 11 (IGSF11), coiled-coil domain 39 molecular ruler complex subunit (CCDC39), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit beta2 (GABRB2), serine protease 35 (PRSS35), solute carrier family 26 member 7 (SLC26A7), astrotactin 2 (ASTN2), cadherin 8 (CDH8), serine and arginine rich splicing factor 12 (SRSF12), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2), chloride intracellular channel 2 (CLIC2), glutamate receptor interacting protein 1 (GRIP1), SH3 domain containing ring finger 2 (SH3RF2), STEAP2 metalloredutase (STEAP2), grainyhead like transcription factor 3 (GRHL3), chloride intracellular channel 6 (CLIC6), actin alpha cardiac muscle 1 (ACTC1), spondin 2 (SPON2), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6B2 (COX6B2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), NHS like 3 (NHSL3 / KIAA1522), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), sphingosine-1-phosphate phosphatase 2 (SGPP2), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 3 (ARHGEF3), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 36 (PPP1R36), serpin family B member 8 (SERPINB8), pleckstrin homology domain containing A7 (PLEKHA7), alanyl aminopeptidase, membrane (ANPEP), myosin IA (MYO1A), glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase 1 (GPD1), dynein axonemal assembly factor 3 (DNAAF3), phospholipase A and acyltransferase 5 (HRASLS5), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein (PHYHIP), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), RAB3B, member RAS oncogene family (RAB3B), mucin 3A, cell surface associated (MUC3A), DLG associated protein 1 (DLGAP1), heparan sulfate 6-O-sulfotransferase 2 (HS6ST2), potassium two pore domain channel subfamily K member 3 (KCNK3), lysophosphatidic acid receptor 3 (LPAR3), anoctamin 5 (ANO5), cilia and flagella associated protein 46 (CFAP46), serine palmitoyltransferase long chain base subunit 3 (SPTLC3), bisphosphoglycerate mutase (BPGM), cold shock domain containing C2 (CSDC2), regulator of calcineurin 2 (RCAN2), radial spoke head component 9 (RSPH9), syntrophin gamma 2 (SNTG2), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), myosin ID (MYO1D), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL), endoplasmic reticulum to nucleus signaling 1 (ERN1), transmembrane protein 125 (TMEM125), calpain 12 (CAPN12), brain expressed X-linked 5 (BEX5), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), RNA binding motif protein 11 (RBM11), transcobalamin 2 (TCN2), NF2, moesin-ezrin-radixin like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), metallophosphoesterase domain containing 1 (MPPED1), pyroglutamylated RFamide peptide receptor (QRFP), natural killer cell cytotoxicity receptor 3 ligand 1 (NCR3LG1), phospholipase A2 group IIA (PLA2G2A), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), tryptase beta 2 (TPSB2), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 1 (ENPP1), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDN-DT), sterol regulatory element binding

transcription factor 2 (SREBF2), collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1) and SEC14 like lipid binding 6 (SEC14L6).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to tabulate 2nd order combinations of USH1C with these genes, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS USH1C									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T USH1C									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
MCUB - USH1C	307	285	1	145	VSIG2 - USH1C	244	161	206	23
TLL1 - USH1C	279	229	78	295	MCOLN3 - USH1C	297	304	124	299
ST6GALNAC2 - USH1C	62	203	216	218	ST6GAL1 - USH1C	176	136	292	222
CAMSAP3 - USH1C	76	210	184	257	CAPN6 - USH1C	184	156	211	302
SCGN - USH1C	208	7	205	250	ABCB1 - USH1C	252	276	202	7
SLC7A8 - USH1C	67	199	223	249	TLL2 - USH1C	157	19	168	211
PACSIN2 - USH1C	143	160	198	173	NTSR1 - USH1C	198	249	48	277
WFDC2 - USH1C	117	295	247	174	ANXA13 - USH1C	223	215	51	265
GRIK5 - USH1C	216	186	146	108	RUNDC3B - USH1C	262	269	37	236
SCNN1A - USH1C	287	96	219	209	FANCE - USH1C	210	240	188	90
PHACTR1 - USH1C	280	224	177	191	RBM24 - USH1C	86	213	152	270
LRRC31 - USH1C	236	163	89	266	PEX5L - USH1C	188	65	275	272
MLPH - USH1C	247	128	227	262	NR5A2 - USH1C	275	193	39	207
PLPPR4 - USH1C	228	103	149	273	PPL - USH1C	144	239	141	223
GALNT12 - USH1C	276	243	217	71	NFE2 - USH1C	61	148	264	275
ABCC4 - USH1C	240	190	159	132	PCSK2 - USH1C	289	50	303	304
TUBA4A - USH1C	95	165	207	179	GNAZ - USH1C	204	253	203	81
FLNC - USH1C	207	19	197	261	MYO5C - USH1C	23	205	163	108
KLK8 - USH1C	259	291	155	8	FGF13 - USH1C	300	238	257	163
PRRG3 - USH1C	305	293	250	32	ASS1 - USH1C	147	166	98	170
BEX2 - USH1C	195	228	215	264	LARGE1 - USH1C	52	187	298	166
UNC79 - USH1C	239	179	137	200	EGF - USH1C	214	208	263	253
BICDL1 - USH1C	112	271	296	290	HECW2 - USH1C	133	214	210	239
KIAA1644 - USH1C	89	248	254	220	COL2A1 - USH1C	237	204	104	268
SLAIN1 - USH1C	250	132	186	140	MDGA2 - USH1C	295	233	21	274
RNF157 - USH1C	222	194	262	91	SLC47A1 - USH1C	189	174	193	76
MAEL - USH1C	249	303	32	301	SUSD4 - USH1C	170	254	221	294
HHIPL2 - USH1C	282	258	212	205	THSD7B - USH1C	164	241	70	230
GALNT13 - USH1C	278	260	256	27	CCDC150 - USH1C	168	151	295	242
IGSF11 - USH1C	231	191	276	252	CCDC39 - USH1C	202	82	285	139
GABRB2 - USH1C	283	292	106	288	PRSS35 - USH1C	211	154	172	161
SLC26A7 - USH1C	165	300	46	256	ASTN2 - USH1C	284	3	235	150

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between USH1C VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t USH1C with USH1C – > MCUB / VSIG2 / TLL1 / MCOLN3 / ST6GALNAC2 / ST6GAL1 / CAMSAP3 / CAPN6 / SCGN / ABCB1 / SLC7A8 / TLL2 / PACSIN2 / NTSR1 / WFDC2 / ANXA13 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B / SCNN1A / FANCE / PHACTR1 / RBM24 / LRRC31 / PEX5L / MLPH / NR5A2 / PLPPR4 / PPL / GALNT12 / NFE2 / ABCC4 / PCSK2 / TUBA4A / GNAZ / FLNC / MYO5C / KLK8 / FGF13 / PRRG3 / ASS1 / BEX2 / LARGE1 / UNC79 / EGF / BICDL1 / HECW2 / KIAA1644 / COL2A1 / SLAIN1 / MDGA2 / RNF157 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS USH1C									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T USH1C									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CDH8 - USH1C	138	266	165	24	SRSF12 - USH1C	199	137	241	201
NCAM2 - USH1C	129	168	259	243	CLIC2 - USH1C	245	138	82	162
GRIP1 - USH1C	169	2	185	215	SH3RF2 - USH1C	272	134	160	233
STEAP2 - USH1C	234	275	228	229	GRHL3 - USH1C	203	263	261	72
CLIC6 - USH1C	288	150	213	98	ACTC1 - USH1C	118	167	136	235
SPON2 - USH1C	77	237	222	144	COX6B2 - USH1C	232	288	24	305
CYP3A4 - USH1C	151	176	255	245	KIAA1522 - USH1C	181	175	111	147
AKNAD1 - USH1C	145	290	68	195	SGPP2 - USH1C	293	236	242	293
ARHGEF3 - USH1C	238	40	281	198	PPP1R36 - USH1C	179	255	124	158
SERPINB8 - USH1C	196	152	196	183	PLEKHA7 - USH1C	174	183	189	194
ANPEP - USH1C	137	10	280	172	MYO1A - USH1C	230	144	173	240
GPD1 - USH1C	258	272	260	121	DNAAF3 - USH1C	273	279	199	56
HRASLS5 - USH1C	268	196	240	35	PHYHIP - USH1C	213	135	265	291
NSG1 - USH1C	185	280	176	226	RAB3B - USH1C	40	220	277	258
MUC3A - USH1C	201	230	268	297	DLGAP1 - USH1C	182	261	258	286
HS6ST2 - USH1C	72	245	151	296	KCNK3 - USH1C	251	155	6	247
LPAR3 - USH1C	291	107	194	259	ANO5 - USH1C	226	209	169	241
CFAP46 - USH1C	131	159	251	178	SPTLC3 - USH1C	186	201	253	232
BPGM - USH1C	45	227	267	184	CSDC2 - USH1C	260	264	182	62
RCAN2 - USH1C	153	146	282	107	RSPH9 - USH1C	267	221	291	251
SNTG2 - USH1C	253	273	25	300	CES4A - USH1C	26	218	154	168
SLCO2A1 - USH1C	146	180	201	99	MYO1D - USH1C	229	262	234	52
LRRN4CL - USH1C	274	59	153	159	ERN1 - USH1C	215	192	305	77
TMEM125 - USH1C	277	259	62	213	CAPN12 - USH1C	154	164	271	58
BEX5 - USH1C	235	234	304	279	SDR42E1 - USH1C	241	212	230	34
RBM11 - USH1C	281	170	174	136	TCN2 - USH1C	183	141	126	203
NF2 - USH1C	292	178	13	269	BCR - USH1C	155	252	192	122
MPPED1 - USH1C	271	242	26	307	QRFPR - USH1C	254	302	19	187
NCR3LG1 - USH1C	148	73	175	189	PLA2G2A - USH1C	263	277	245	306
SLC6A9 - USH1C	194	267	243	123	TPSB2 - USH1C	9	246	162	254
ENPP1 - USH1C	172	81	144	267	AFDN-DT - USH1C	227	13	135	255
SREBF2 - USH1C	106	189	307	155	COL15A1 - USH1C	161	24	238	185
SEC14L6 - USH1C	200	157	287	39	- USH1C				

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between USH1C VS Individual members.

SLC47A1 / MAEL / SUSD4 / HHIPL2 / THSD7B / GALNT13 / CCDC150 / IGSF11 / CCDC39 / GABRB2 / PRSS35 / SLC26A7 / ASTN2 / CDH8 / SRSF12 / NCAM2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / SH3RF2 / STEAP2 / GRHL3 / CLIC6 / ACTC1 / SPON2 / COX6B2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / ARHGEF3 / PPP1R36 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / ANPEP / MYO1A / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / HRASLS5 / PHYHIP / NSG1 / RAB3B / MUC3A / DLGAP1 / HS6ST2 / KCNK3 / LPAR3 / ANO5 / CFAP46 / SPTLC3 / BPGM / CSDC2 / RCAN2 / RSPH9 / SNTG2 / CES4A / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / LRRN4CL / ERN1 / TMEM125 / CAPN12 / BEX5 / SDR42E1 / RBM11 / TCN2 / NF2 / BCR / MPPED1 / QRFPR / NCR3LG1 / PLA2G2A / SLC6A9 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SREBF2 / COL15A1 / SEC14L6.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t USH1C	
MCUB / VSIG2 / TLL1 / MCOLN3 / ST6GALNAC2 ...	
ST6GAL1 / CAMSAP3 / CAPN6 / SCGN / ABCB1 ...	
SLC7A8 / TLL2 / PACSIN2 / NTSR1 / WFDC2 ...	
ANXA13 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B / SCNN1A / FANCE ...	
PHACTR1 / RBM24 / LRRC31 / PEX5L / MLPH ...	
NR5A2 / PLPPR4 / PPL / GALNT12 / NFE2 ...	
ABCC4 / PCSK2 / TUBA4A / GNAZ / FLNC ...	
MYO5C / KLK8 / FGF13 / PRRG3 / ASS1 / BEX2 ...	
LARGE1 / UNC79 / EGF / BICDL1 / HECW2 ...	
KIAA1644 / COL2A1 / SLAIN1 / MDGA2 / ...	
RNF157 / SLC47A1 / MAEL / SUSD4 / HHIPL2 ...	
THSD7B / GALNT13 / CCDC150 / IGSF11 ...	
CCDC39 / GABRB2 / PRSS35 / SLC26A7 / ASTN2 ...	
CDH8 / SRSF12 / NCAM2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 ...	
SH3RF2 / STEAP2 / GRHL3 / CLIC6 / ACTC1 ...	
SPON2 / COX6B2 / CYP3A4 / KIAA1522 / AKNAD1 ...	
SGPP2 / ARHGEF3 / PPP1R36 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 ...	
ANPEP / MYO1A / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / HRASLS5 ...	
PHYHIP / NSG1 / RAB3B / MUC3A / DLGAP1 ...	
HS6ST2 / KCNK3 / LPAR3 / ANO5 / CFAP46 ...	
SPTLC3 / BPGM / CSDC2 / RCAN2 / RSPH9 ...	
SNTG2 / CES4A / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / LRRN4CL ...	
ERN1 / TMEM125 / CAPN12 / BEX5 / SDR42E1 ...	
RBM11 / TCN2 / NF2 / BCR / MPPED1 / QRFPR ...	
NCR3LG1 / PLA2G2A / SLC6A9 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 ...	
AFDN-DT / SREBF2 / COL15A1 / SEC14L6	USH1C

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between USH1C and Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic USH1C 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of USH1C-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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